

FT2 Sustainable Control of *Plasmopara viticola* in Grapevines via SafeWax: A Bioinspired Passive Coating Strategy

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SafeWax is a bioinspired antifungal coating designed as a sustainable alternative to conventional fungicides. Its fatty acid-based formulation mimics the superhydrophobic and self-cleaning properties of natural cuticles of superhydrophobic plants, forming a stable, water-repellent barrier that hinders pathogen adhesion and colonization while ensuring sustainable, environmentally friendly protection. *In-vitro* assays on grapevine leaf discs demonstrated complete inhibition of *Plasmopara viticola* at a SafeWax dosage of 35 $\mu\text{L}/\text{cm}^2$. Treatments applied both prior to and following pathogen inoculation indicated that SafeWax primarily exerts preventive and protective effects rather than curative action. Long-term efficacy was confirmed through *in-vivo* trials on whole grapevine plants. Leaves inoculated up to 9 days post coating application consistently showed significant pathogen suppression, with inhibition rates ranging from 47% to 80% when compared to uncoated leaves, showing a substantial protective activity over time. Coating persistence was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on leaves 3, 6, 20, and 40 days after application, revealing strong adhesion and stable structural integrity, essential for prolonged field effectiveness. Ongoing field trials are running to assess SafeWax applicability under standard vineyard conditions, comparing its performance with conventional and organic treatments including copper and essential oil-based fungicides. Overall, SafeWax offers a promising passive strategy to reduce synthetic inputs while maintaining effective grapevine protection.

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